

EXPLORING THE EFFECT OF PEACE EDUCATION INTERVENTION ON THE KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDES OF MYANMAR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of this study is to promote awareness among pre-service teachers regarding peace education in Myanmar. It seeks to explore whether the peace education intervention has any effect on the knowledge and attitudes of pre-service teachers. This study was conducted using the quasi-experimental design and a semi-structured interview as a qualitative approach to determine pre-service teachers' knowledge and attitudes toward promoting peace education. The peace education intervention program was conducted during the 2nd and 3rd weeks of June 2025. The participants included 35 pre-service teachers from the selected education degree college, of whom 6 participants were chosen for the semi-structured interviews. Data analysis was performed using thematic analysis, and the results indicated that pre-service teachers' definitions of peace reflect their real-life situations based on their experiences. Moreover, pre-service teachers believed that peace education is an essential element for the country's development and serves as a tool for resolving conflicts that affect children's learning opportunities. Most pre-service teachers demonstrated an enhanced understanding of peace education and its values, along with a more positive mindset and greater self-awareness. It was found that they experienced significant changes in both their knowledge and attitudes, achieving all the intended objectives through the intervention within three days, indicating that it was effective to some extent. This study suggests that integrating peace education into teacher training programs can effectively promote peace education.

KEYWORDS

Peace Education Intervention, Knowledge and Attitudes, Myanmar Pre-Service Teachers

1. INTRODUCTION

Peace is an essential element for the development of a nation and sustainable development cannot be achieved without peace. While it may not be accurate to assert that all peaceful nations are fully developed, it is undeniable that a lack of peace significantly hampers a country's potential for development. The Global Peace Index (GPI) ranks countries around the world based on their levels of peacefulness, and as of 2025, Myanmar is positioned at 153 out of 163 countries, indicating its status as one of the least peaceful nations in Southeast Asia [1]. Myanmar is a country with numerous challenges, including ethnic tensions, violence, prejudice, intolerance, and extremism within its society.

Myanmar is highly ethnically diverse, with 135 ethnicities officially recognized by the government [2,3]. The Burman or Bamar ethnic group is the majority, with perhaps two thirds of the population, while ethnic communities _the major being the Shan, Karen, Rakhine, Mon, Kachin, Chin and

Kayah_ are thought to collectively account for perhaps one third of the population [3,4]. Moreover, Myanmar has been experiencing the ethnic conflicts for over seven decades since after its independence in 1948, based on the lack of trust and mutual understanding among the government, majority ethnic Burmese group and other minority ethnic groups [3]. It is evident that Myanmar urgently needs to build peace and promote peace education by encouraging coexistence, cooperation, and the acceptance of cultural and ethnic diversity [5].

While conflicts are not deniable in any society, particularly in a diverse and multicultural one, the solutions employed to approach these issues are crucial and significantly affect the residents of that society. Although education alone cannot resolve the ongoing crises and conflicts, it plays a vital role in peacebuilding by fostering the values of peace and nurturing future generations to manage conflicts in more constructive and peaceful manners.

Peace education encompasses the teaching of values, attitudes, and competencies necessary for resolving conflicts non-violently and fostering harmonious relationships. Such skills are crucial for the citizens of Myanmar which is a diverse and multi-ethnic society, to coexist peacefully and harmoniously [5]. The concept of promoting peace through education is not a new idea since it has been practiced informally throughout human history. Traditions of conflict resolution have been transmitted across generations by contributing to the promotion of peace within communities [6,7].

Peace education equips students with peace cultivating and peace promoting skills which enable them to comprehend personal and societal issues and limitations and identify the root causes of conflicts [7,8,9,10]. These skills also encourage them to manage personal and interpersonal conflicts and analyze various forms of violence including cultural, environmental and global that occur beyond the classroom setting [7,8].

Students who participate in peace education generally adapt themselves to various situations, including critical thinking, decision-making, interactions, negotiations, resolving conflicts, encouraging peace and preventing violence [11]. Undoubtedly, teachers are key in furnishing students with these skills. Teachers are a crucial factor for undertaking vital responsibility of achieving peace education values. That is why teachers should be equipped with universal values, such as freedom, justice, human rights, gender equality, tolerance and respect for the right to live. They should also develop an understanding of peace and a desire for an internalized peaceful culture. Forming such values may be possible through pre-service education [11].

Similarly, Arain, Ramzan & Noshab [7] argued that the effectiveness of teaching peace education is only possible when a teacher has sufficient knowledge and essential pedagogical skills to construct peace in the tender minds of children. Teachers should be given necessary training not only to teach peace education, but also developing students' attitudes and skills [12]. Thus, integration of peace education in teacher education programs and in school curriculum can be very helpful in constructing, developing and promoting peace.

Thus, this study aims to conduct an intervention program in relation to peace education including concept and values of peace education, conflict resolution techniques, and the role of teachers in promoting peace education. It also aims to promote pre-service teachers' awareness about peace education by creating group activities and encouraging them to discuss and share their existing knowledge with one another and explore the impact of peace education intervention on their knowledge and attitudes.

1.1. Purpose of the Study

The original purpose of this study is to promote the awareness of pre-service teachers in relating to promoting peace education in Myanmar by conducting a Peace Education Intervention. Assessing the impact of the intervention on pre-service teachers is an essential component. Thus, it aims to explore the effect of Peace Education Intervention on the knowledge and attitudes of Myanmar pre-service teachers. Based on the main aim, the study addressed the following research questions.

- How do pre-service teachers view on the concept of peace and values of peace education?
- How do pre-service teachers perceive on the concept of conflicts, violence and conflict resolution strategies?
- How do pre-service teachers perceive the promotion of peace education in Myanmar and the role of teachers in the process?
- Are there any changes in pre-service teachers' knowledge and attitudes before and after the intervention?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Although most people today emphasize globalization, there are contradictions and inconsistencies arising from local and international conflicts and crises around the world. Consequently, the importance of peace and peace education has become crucial in both educational settings and social sciences. In recent years, various researchers, educators, and authors around the world have been exploring the field of peace education and dealing with promotion of peace education.

Mishra (2011) explored pre-service teacher training for peace education in order to assess B.Ed. students' awareness of peace education [13], while Polat (2016) conducted a qualitative study to investigate the perspectives of prospective teachers who participated in a peace education program, focusing on the qualities of teachers. The results revealed that participants who attended the program not only grasped the concept of peace education but also enhanced their awareness of the qualities needed in educators who teach it [14]. Additionally, Amin, Jumani and Malik (2020) also examined the views of teacher educators and prospective teachers regarding the integration of peace education in teacher education and concluded that peace education develops positive thinking, knowledge, self-awareness and compassion among teachers [15].

Similarly, the findings of the research conducted by Gul (2020) indicated that practices of the leaders and teachers are important to promote peace education [16]. Moreover, several studies have explored the impact of peace education on the knowledge and attitudes of pre-service teachers through experimental research. For instance, Arain, Ramzan and Noshab (2019) assessed the effectiveness of teacher training in cultivating peace and they concluded that the training was successful leading to a positive impact on pre-service teachers' understanding and skills related to peace education [7]. Similarly, the findings of Bashir and Akbar (2021) also indicated that peace education intervention achieved its intended objectives resulting in improved knowledge and attitudes among participants towards peace education [17].

In response to changing local and global needs, many institutes around the world are offering courses and programs related or supportive to peace and peace education [7]. However, with a focus on the local needs of Myanmar, peace education through conflict resolution should be emphasized, and the role of teachers in promoting peace education should also be highlighted. Therefore, this intervention program can be considered one of those programs aimed at enhancing pre-service teachers' awareness and understanding of peace education and its values.

2.1. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study based on constructivism learning theory and ASK model for Peace Education which is framed in accordance to the guidelines of Peace Education Handbook for teachers and educators for the Great Lake Regions (2021). According to ASK model, the purpose and function in general and peace education specially is not to convey the necessary knowledge (what), and the required skills (how), but most importantly it needs to teach the values (why) [18]. On the other hand, constructivist conceptions of learning consider learners as an active agent in the process of knowledge acquisition. Students learn by fitting new information together with what they already know. Constructivism also promotes social and communication skills by creating a classroom environment that emphasizes collaboration and exchange of ideas. Students therefore exchange ideas and then negotiate with others. They suggest that people construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world, through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences [19,20]. Exchange of ideas by negotiating with others promotes social and communication skills in terms of creating a classroom environment that emphasizes collaboration and exchange of ideas.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

In this study, the quasi-experimental design i.e., one group pretest – posttest design was employed to explore the impact of the Peace Education Intervention on the knowledge and attitudes of pre-service teachers. Pre-tests, post-tests, and reflective questions were utilized to assess the impact of the intervention program and the changes in knowledge and attitudes. A semi-structured interview was conducted following the intervention.

3.2. Participants of the Study

Participants were selected by purposive sampling method and they were 35 pre-service teachers of selected Education Degree College of Myanmar who were fourth year students. They represent different ethnic groups of different regions where some regions are almost peaceful, some are civil wars crisis areas and some places are neither fully peaceful nor completely unpeaceful that is civil wars are happened in the nearest areas of their regions. Participants' demographic characteristics are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the participants

No.	Student	Gender	Academic Year and Sections	Hometowns	Peacefulness Level of Hometowns
1	M1	Male	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
2	M2	Male	4 th Year (A)	Taunggyi	Peaceful
3	M3	Male	4 th Year (D)	Minking	Not peaceful
4	M4	Male	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
5	M5	Male	4 th Year (A)	Pinlaung	Not peaceful
6	M6	Male	4 th Year (D)	Pinlaung	Peaceful
7	M7	Male	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
8	M8	Male	4 th Year (A)	Ywangan	Mid peaceful
9	M9	Male	4 th Year (A)	Yatsaut	Not peaceful
10	M10	Male	4 th Year (C)	Hopone	Mid peaceful
11	M11	Male	4 th Year (D)	Hopone	Peaceful
12	M12	Male	4 th Year (B)	Pindaya	Peaceful
13	F1	Female	4 th Year (A)	Kyaukse	Peaceful
14	F2	Female	4 th Year (B)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
15	F3	Female	4 th Year (B)	Phekhong	Not peaceful
16	F4	Female	4 th Year (C)	Sisaing	Mid peaceful
17	F5	Female	4 th Year (B)	Sisaing	Mid peaceful
18	F6	Female	4 th Year (A)	Nyaungshwe	Peaceful
19	F7	Female	4 th Year (A)	Taunggyi	Peaceful
20	F8	Female	4 th Year (C)	Pego	Mid peaceful
21	F9	Female	4 th Year (A)	Phekhong	Not peaceful
22	F10	Female	4 th Year (D)	Hehoe	Mid peaceful
23	F11	Female	4 th Year (D)	Ywangan	Not peaceful
24	F12	Female	4 th Year (A)	Yatsaut	Mid peaceful
25	F13	Female	4 th Year (A)	Kalaw	Peaceful
26	F14	Female	4 th Year (A)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
27	F15	Female	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Not peaceful
28	F16	Female	4 th Year (A)	Minekaing	Not peaceful
29	F17	Female	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Mid peaceful
30	F18	Female	4 th Year (D)	Nyaungshwe	Peaceful
31	F19	Female	4 th Year (D)	Phekhong	Not peaceful
32	F20	Female	4 th Year (D)	Pindaya	Peaceful
33	F21	Female	4 th Year (C)	Pinlaung	Not peaceful
34	F22	Female	4 th Year (A)	Sisaing	Mid peaceful
35	F23	Female	4 th Year (A)	Hopone	Mid peaceful

3.3. Procedures of Peace Education Intervention

To conduct the Peace Education Intervention, necessary documents—including an explanation of the experimental research, a request for cooperation from the principal and participants, and a research ethics checklist—were submitted to Okayama University. Expert validity was achieved with the guidance of the supervisor and two professors from Education Degree Colleges of Myanmar during the preparation of the questionnaires. Once permission was obtained from the Department of Teacher Education in Myanmar, the procedures were initiated.

Peace Education Intervention was conducted based on Peace Education Handbook for the Great Lake Regions (2021). Demographic questions, pre-test and post-test which include both closed-

ended questions, open-ended questions and reflective questions were prepared in order to assess pre-service teachers' knowledge and attitudes towards peace education and the role of teachers for promoting peace education in Myanmar. After selecting 35 participants by purposive sampling method, the selected pre-service teachers were asked to take the pre-test before the intervention lessons. It took about two weeks (2nd and 3rd week of June, 2025) to complete the intervention. Peace Education lessons were conveyed to pre-service teachers within 3 days and each lesson took about an hour including discussion and group activities. After the intervention, post-test with some reflective questions were asked in order to analyze their changes. The procedures of the intervention are described in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Procedures of Peace Education Intervention

The closed-ended questions include

- (1) Have you ever heard ASK model?
- (2) Do you know the meaning of A, S and K of the model?
- (3) Do you think conflict and violence are the same?
- (4) Do you know conflict resolution techniques?
- (5) Do you think peace education should be promoted in Myanmar?
- (6) Do you think teachers are important in promoting peace education?
- (7) Do you think knowledge and skills of a teacher are important in promoting peace education?
- (8) Do you think you are one of the important persons for promoting peace education?

The open-ended questions and reflective questions consist of

- (1) How will you define the concept of peace?
- (2) How do you understand the concept of conflict?
- (3) How do you understand the concept of violence?
- (4) What are the values of peace education?
- (5) Please describe conflict resolution techniques?
- (6) Why should peace education be promoted in Myanmar?
- (7) What did you know by attending this 3-day training? (post-test only)
- (8) Have there been any changes in your idea or attitudes? What have you changed after the training? (post-test only)

(9) What could you do to promote peace education in Myanmar if you become a teacher?
(post-test only)

The topics, contents and expected outcomes of the lessons were described in Table (2).

Table 2. The topics, contents and expected outcomes of the Peace Education Intervention

Intervention	Topic of the lesson	Contents of the lesson	Expected Outcomes
Day 1	Introduction to the Concept of Peace and the elements of a Peaceful Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Group discussion about own's meaning of peace and introducing the concept of peace by different cultures (Indian's "Shanti", Japanese "Heiwa" and African "Ubuntu"). ▪ Discussion about dimensions of peace and let the pre-service teachers think about "the essential elements of a Peaceful society". (Group activities by using charts) ▪ "The Positive Peace Pillars for a society" and "elements for a peaceful society" by Peace Education Handbook. (Group activities by using charts) 	To have an awareness about the broad concept of peace from different cultures and recognize the important elements to build a peaceful society.
Day 2	Nature of Peace Education and Values of Peace Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to "peace education by UNICEF (2016)" and discuss about the values of peace education by identifying each concept. ▪ Discussion about "ASK Model by Peace Education Handbook for Great Lake Regions, 2021" and "ASK Model by Peace Education Training Manual for Southeast Asia, 2015". 	To have an awareness about the concept and values of peace education and recognize the importance of knowledge, skills and attitudes of teachers for implementing peace education.

Day 3	Peace Education as an Instrument for Conflict Resolution and the Role of Teachers in Promoting Peace Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to “the nature of conflict, violence and types of violence by Peace Education Handbook (2021)” and discuss about the concept of conflict resolution and techniques of peaceful conflict resolution. ▪ Discussion about “peace education as an instrument for conflict resolution and the role of teacher as a mediator or a leader in promoting peace education”. 	To have a clear understanding the difference between conflicts and violence and the importance of peaceful conflict resolution techniques and the teachers’ roles for promoting peace education.
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3.4. Data Analysis

For data analysis, thematic analysis was employed for analyzing, coding, and interpreting the data. The analysis followed the six steps developed by Braun and Clarke (2006): Familiarization, Coding, Generating Themes, Reviewing Themes, Defining and Naming Themes, and Writing Up.

4. RESULTS

The findings were presented by three sections which include (1) pre-service teachers’ perceptions on the concept of peace, conflict, violence, conflict resolution techniques and the values of peace education, (2) the impact of peace education intervention on their knowledge and attitudes in relation to promoting peace education and (3) semi-structured interview result.

4.1. Pre-service teachers’ perceptions on the concept of peace, conflict, violence, conflict resolution techniques and values of peace education

In order to explore how pre-service teachers perceive on the concept of peace, conflict, violence, conflict resolution techniques and values of peace education, the questions mentioned in the methodology are used in the pre-test before the intervention. The responses were analyzed by thematic analysis and shown by tables.

Table 3. Perceptions of pre-service teachers on the concept of peace

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Freedom of movement and peaceful daily living	9
2	Harmony and peaceful coexistence	9
3	Security of body and mind / inner peace	8
4	Having justice, equality and human rights	7
5	Absence of conflict, violence and war	6
6	Freedom of expression and communication	2

According to Table 3, it was found that their definitions of peace encompass the freedom to live and move safely in daily life, harmonious coexistence with others, security of body and mind, the presence of justice, equality, and human rights, the absence of violence and war, and the freedom to express and communicate without fear.

Table 4. Perceptions of pre-service teachers on the concept of conflict

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Disagreement between two people or two groups	22
2	Problems due to disagreement because of different views	9
3	Arguments or fights (less severe or verbal conflict)	8
4	Internal or intra-group problems	7
5	Competition between two people or groups	6
6	No response	2

It was found that most of the pre-service teachers think that conflicts are result of disagreement between two people or two groups because of different perspectives according to Table 4.

Table 5. Perceptions of pre-service teachers on the concept of Violence

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Intended harm or making someone suffer	8
2	Bullying or victimization (general)	7
3	Bullying or victimization for personal benefit	6
4	Victimization by using power	5
5	Violence by using weapons	3
6	Coercion or pressure	2
7	No response	1

According to Table 5, it was found that pre-service teachers think that violence is an intended action to make someone suffer by giving pressure or using weapons or power harassment.

Table 6. Perceptions of pre-service teachers on conflict resolution techniques

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Negotiation	18
2	Discussion and Adjustment	7
3	Accepting differences	3
4	Peaceful communication	2
5	No response	11

According to Table 6, although 11 out of 35 pre-service teachers didn't give any response, it can be seen that most of the pre-service teachers consider negotiation and discussion as peaceful conflict resolution techniques and they think it is important to accept individual differences to solve conflicts peacefully.

Table 7. Perceptions of pre-service teachers on the values of peace education

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Empathy, respect and moral values	12
2	Freedom, justice, equality and human rights	11
3	responsibility and cooperation	6
4	Conflict resolution, negotiation and coexistence	5
5	Positive mindset and emotional well-being	3
6	No response	1

According to Table 7, it was found that pre-service teachers consider moral values as empathy, respect, responsibility and some democracy values as freedom, justice and human rights as values of education.

4.2. The Impact of peace education intervention on the knowledge and attitudes of pre-service teachers

In this section, the findings were presented by dividing into (1) closed-ended questions and (2) open-ended questions and reflective questions, which constitutes both knowledge and attitude-based questions.

4.2.1. Closed-Ended Questions

Closed-ended questions were asked in both pre-test and post-test. By comparing pre-service teachers' responses shown in Table 8, it was found that almost all the pre-service teachers have never heard of ASK model and the meaning of each word. However, they could answer the meaning of each word correctly in the post test. Only one student believed that conflict and violence were the same; however, he was able to understand the difference between the two after the training. Similarly, in relation to conflict resolution techniques, it was found that 11 students didn't know and give any responses in the pre-test while 24 students answered only one or two resolution techniques they think. They, however, could answer all the conflict resolution techniques correctly in the post test. On the other hand, all 35 students thought that teachers and their knowledge and skills are important for promoting peace education. Lastly, among 35 students, 2 students thought that they are not one of the important persons for promoting peace education before the intervention and it was found that they changed their attitude after the intervention.

Table 8. Results of closed-ended questions before and after the Intervention

No	Closed-ended Questions	Pre-Intervention		Post-Intervention	
		Yes	No	Yes	No
1	Have you ever heard ASK model?	1	34	35	0
2	Do you know the meaning of A, S and K of the model?	1	34	35	0
3	Do you think conflict and violence are the same?	1	34	0	35
4	Do you know conflict resolution techniques?	24	11	35	0
5	Do you think peace education should be promoted in Myanmar?	35	0	35	0
6	Do you think teachers are important in promoting peace education?	35	0	35	0
7	Do you think knowledge and skills of a teacher are important in promoting peace education?	35	0	35	0
8	Do you think you are one of the important persons for promoting peace education?	33	2	35	0

4.2.2. Open-ended questions and reflective questions

This section presents pre-service teachers' perceptions on the reason why peace education should be promoted in Myanmar and their reflections on the learning and changes they experienced following the intervention. It also addresses their intentions to advocate for peace education in the country.

Table 9. The reasons why peace education should be promoted in Myanmar

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Peace as a foundation for National Development	10
2	Impact of conflicts on educational access and children's learning opportunities	8
3	Need of peace education for the people's mindset change	7
4	Ethnic diversity and national unity challenges	8
5	Social harmony and connections among the citizens	3
6	General national conditions and underdevelopment	3

According to Table 9, it was found that pre-service teachers think that peace education is essential for national development, educational access, social harmony, and unity in a diverse society, while ongoing conflict contributes to underdevelopment and the need for peace education to change people's mindsets.

Table 10. Pre-service teachers' reflections on their learning after the Intervention

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Definitions and meaning of peace & peace education	6
2	Values of peace & peace education	20
3	Conflict resolution techniques	19
4	Nature and differences between conflicts and violence	13
5	Essential elements & pillars of a peaceful society	8
6	Role of teaches in peace education	8
7	ASK model (Attitude, Skills, Knowledge)	5
8	Importance of peace education in peacebuilding and national development	7
9	Personal reflection and Self-awareness	4

According to the reflections of pre-service teachers as shown in Table 10, it was found that participants learned the meaning and values of peace, the differences between conflict and violence, effective conflict resolution skills, the attitudes, skills, and knowledge needed for peacebuilding, and the important role of teachers and individuals in creating a peaceful society and supporting national development.

Table 11. Pre-service teachers' reflections on their changes after the Intervention

No	Themes	No. of Responses
1	Gained understanding of the concept, values, and importance of peace education.	18
2	Described changes in mindset, self-awareness and a desire for personal transformation after training.	12
3	Highlighted realizations about personal responsibility and contributions in peacebuilding or promoting peace.	9
4	Realized the importance of teachers in shaping peace.	10
5	Became equipped to resolve conflicts peacefully.	8
6	Understood how peace education contributes to broader societal, economic or national progress.	6

It was found that participants demonstrated improved understanding of peace education and its values, positive mindset and self-awareness changes, stronger conflict resolution abilities, greater recognition of personal and teachers' roles in peacebuilding, and clearer awareness of peace education's contribution to societal and national development as shown in Table 11.

Table 12. Pre-service teachers' intention for promoting peace education

No	Themes	Descriptors	No. of Responses
1	Self-transformation before sharing	Committing to change one's own mindset, behavior, or values before engaging in promoting peace education.	14
2	Sharing peace education knowledge	Commitment to disseminating knowledge and values peace education to others.	16
3	Teaching peace education to children	Educating and instilling peace values in students and children.	10
4	Acting as a mediator in conflict resolution	Mediation by applying peaceful conflict resolution methods in real situations.	10
5	Leadership and advocacy role	Taking on leadership or advocacy roles in peacebuilding.	3

According to Table 12, it was found that pre-service teachers think that self-fulfilling about peace education, transmitting knowledge and acting as a mediator and leader would be effective to promote peace education.

4.3. Semi-structured Interview Results

A semi-structured interview was conducted after the post-test of the intervention program, selecting only six from the 35 attendees. The aim of the interview was to gain a deeper understanding of their reflections on the intervention program and their attitudes toward promoting peace education. The criteria for selecting participants included the location and level of peacefulness in their hometowns, as well as their ethnicity. The list of the participants was shown in table 13.

Table 13. Pre-service teachers who participated in semi-structured interview

No	Gender	Hometown	Peacefulness Level of Hometown	Ethnicity	4 th Year Section
1	Female	Pinlaung, Southern Shan State	Mid peaceful	Pao	Section (B)
2	Female	Phekhong, Shan- Kayar Border	Unpeaceful	Kayan+Bamar	Section (B)
3	Female	Kyaukse, Mandalay Region	Peaceful	Bamar	Section (A)
4	Male	Taunggyi, Capital of Shan State	Peaceful	Bamar	Section (A)
5	Male	Pinlaung, Southern Shan State	Mid peaceful	Pao	Section (C)
6	Male	Minking, Sagaing Region	Unpeaceful	Chin+Bamar	Section (D)

Semi-structured interview was conducted for 15 to 20 minutes for each participant by using audio-recording method. The questions used in the interview were as follows.

1. What is your ethnic group?
2. Please describe your hometown and choose its peacefulness level _ peaceful, mid peaceful or unpeaceful? (Already told the criteria of the levels)
3. Are there any impacts or sufferings among your family members or relatives because of the civil wars or conflicts in the country?
4. How do you feel about the civil wars or conflicts in the country?
5. Do you think Myanmar needs to promote Peace Education? Why or why not?
6. Do you think teachers are important in promoting Peace Education? At which level do you think they are important?
7. Have there been any changes in your knowledge or attitudes because of this 3-day training? Why do you think so?
8. If you become a teacher, what do you want to do to promote peace education?

In this paper, the summary and key points of the interview would be discussed.

By concerning about the feelings upon the conflicts and civil wars in the country, the participants expressed of fear, insecurity, sadness and emotional distress arising from exposure to civil wars either directly or through the social media consumption. Some of the participants (2 and 6) especially, are unable to return home and they have to face family separation and financial difficulties resulting from ongoing conflict and instability. Most of the participants reflected from their experiences the emergence of empathy towards affected populations and active participation in humanitarian support such as providing food. The participant 6 who is from civil war region, showed perception of fairness and injustice regarding access to education, emphasizing that political instability should not limit students' learning opportunities.

When they are asked their opinions regarding the role and importance level of teachers in promoting peace education, it was found that participants 3 and 4 who are from peaceful regions, thought that teachers are the primary agents and the most responsible people to promote peace education. In contrast, participants 1 and 5 from moderately peaceful regions perceived the importance of teachers to be in the second position and believe that promoting peace education is closely related to individual and parental attitudes. the other hand, participants 2 and 6 who are civil war affected areas, viewed teachers are not the most important persons compared to the national government and educational institutions. Participant 6 believed that establishing stability in the country should be the top priority, followed by economic development as the second priority, and promoting peace education as the third priority.

In exploring their reflections on the intervention program, as well as their attitudes and changes before and after the intervention, participants 1, 4, and 6 replied that they developed foundational conceptual knowledge about peace and conflict, deepening their theoretical awareness about peace education. Participants 2 and 6 indicated that the training influenced their values and emotional responses, fostering non-violent perspectives and peace-oriented thinking. Meanwhile, participants 3 and 4 began to view themselves as active contributors to peace education, gaining confidence and a sense of responsibility as future educators. Most participants believed that learning occurred through interactive processes and practical skill development, by emphasizing the importance of group discussion and reflection.

Moreover, regarding their intentions and future plans for promoting peace education, they emphasize the importance of transmitting peace values and encouraging non-violent approaches to conflict resolution (participants 1, 2, and 4). Similarly, they seek to integrate peace education into students' daily lives and classroom practices rather than limiting it to textbooks and curricula

(participants 1, 3, and 6). Additionally, they aim to cultivate students' ethical character, sense of responsibility, and critical thinking skills as central outcomes of peace education (participants 4 and 6). Finally, they perceive themselves as role models and stress the significance of their own continuous learning and professional development in the field of peace education (participants 2 and 5).

5. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

According to the findings from the pre-intervention phase, pre-service teachers' definitions of peace reflect their real-life situations based on their experiences, as many live in regions where dangerous situations can arise when moving from place to place, leading to feelings of insecurity. They also viewed conflict as a disagreement between individuals or groups, stemming from different perspectives, competition for resources, or internal problems, often expressed through arguments, fights, or violence. They defined violence as intentional harm or suffering inflicted on others through bullying, abuse of power, coercion, or the use of weapons, frequently for personal benefit. Nearly half of them were unaware of peaceful conflict resolution techniques, while the other half considered negotiation and discussion to be common methods. Moreover, they regarded moral values such as empathy, respect, and responsibility, along with democratic values like freedom, justice, and human rights, as values of peace education.

Similarly, according to the reflective responses, pre-service teachers believed that peace education is an essential element for the development of the country and serves as a tool for resolving conflicts that affect children's learning opportunities. It was also found that they could achieve all the intended objectives through the intervention within three days, indicating that it was effective to some extent.

After the intervention, most of the pre-service teachers showed an enhanced understanding of peace education and its values, with a more positive mindset and greater self-awareness. They also exhibited a better understanding of conflict resolution skills and how peace education contributes to societal and national development and a deeper recognition of both their personal roles and those of teachers in peacebuilding. Finally, pre-service teachers demonstrated their desire to engage in self-fulfillment regarding peace education by transmitting knowledge and acting as mediators and leaders for the effective implementation of peace education.

By comparing the responses of pre-intervention and post-intervention phases, it was found that they had significant positive changes both in their knowledge and attitudes. This finding was consistent with the previous study conducted by Bashir (2021)[17], which focused on implementing peace education and checking its effectiveness on prospective teachers' knowledge and attitudes and improvement in the knowledge and attitudes of participants towards peace was observed. Since the main purpose of the intervention program was to promote pre-service teachers' awareness towards peace education and to analyze the impact of the intervention, it can be concluded that the intervention had an impact on the knowledge and attitude of pre-service teachers.

However, it is important to acknowledge that this study has limitations, particularly regarding the duration of the intervention program, which lasted only for two weeks. Although the intention was to develop the lessons over at least a month, this was impossible due to scheduling conflicts faced by the pre-service teachers, as they were occupied with their practicum and regular class schedules. Additionally, a major challenge was that the researcher was studying abroad, which provided only a limited time to return to Myanmar for conducting the research. A longer-term experimental study would be beneficial to obtain more validated results. Future research should also consider implementing an experimental design that includes both a control group and an experimental group to better evaluate the impact of the intervention program.

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